

1 **Conference report:**

2 Indo-Swiss Symposium on Personalized Oncology with a theme on Precision Oncology: The
3 Future of Cancer Care – A Conference Report

4 **Report compiled by:**

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9 **Abstract:**

10 The Indo-Swiss symposium on precision oncology for the future of cancer care was conducted as
11 part of Indo-Swiss collaborative project titled ‘Molecular and Pharmacogenetic marker evaluation
12 in relation to the toxicity and clinical response of Acute Lymphoblastic Leukemia (ALL) treatment
13 in Indian children’. The main objective of this symposium is to discuss on topics such as precision
14 oncology practice using somatic genetic information, therapeutic drug monitoring, and
15 pharmacogenomics with an emphasis given to Paediatric oncology setting. The program involved
16 scientific presentations, panel discussion and a debate that has been appreciated well by the
17 attendees and emphasized the requirement of such events on regular basis as a continued medical
18 education program in their feedback.

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20 **Keywords:** Paediatric oncology, therapeutic drug monitoring, pharmacogenomics, LMIC,
21 translational oncology.

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24 The Indo-Swiss symposium on precision oncology for the future of cancer care was conducted as
25 part of Indo-Swiss collaborative project titled ‘Molecular and Pharmacogenetic marker evaluation
26 in relation to the toxicity and clinical response of Acute Lymphoblastic Leukemia (ALL) treatment
27 in Indian children (MPG_x-INDALL)’. The symposium was jointly organized by Dr. Biswajit
28 Dubashi, Department of Medical Oncology, Jawaharlal Institute of Postgraduate Medical
29 Education and Research (JIPMER), Puducherry, and Dr. Chakradhara Rao S Uppugunduri,
30 CANSEARCH Research Platform on Paediatric Oncology and Hematology, University of
31 Geneva, Switzerland. The symposium took place in hybrid mode on November 21, 2022, at
32 JIPMER, Puducherry, India.

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34 The symposium provided detailed discussion on the era of precision oncology to implement
35 personalized medicine in clinical settings to improve the future of cancer care. The program was
36 divided into two sessions, the first session was on diagnostics and research, consisted of four
37 lectures and a panel discussion. The second session was on therapeutics and research, consisted of
38 four lectures and a debate. The resource persons for the symposium were eminent national and
39 international experts (supplementary material). A total of 75 delegates participated either in person
40 or virtually. Most of the delegates were students (42%), faculty members (32.1%), medical
41 residents (21.9%), and industrial delegates (4%) from the Indian subcontinent.

42

43 The first keynote lecture of the program started with an interactive talk delivered by Professor
44 Sameer Bakhshi on the topic "**Challenges and Opportunities in translational oncology from
45 an Indian Perspective: Focus on Oncology**". He began highlighting the need-based research to
46 improvise clinical practice settings or outcomes along with the necessity to identify collaborations

47 to conduct research. He also spoke about the challenges faced by low-middle-income countries
48 (LMIC) due to limited resources to handle the disease burden and unaffordability of the modern
49 medicines. Then he discussed about innovative metronomic chemotherapy, which is a form of
50 anti-angiogenic chemotherapy administered at regular intervals that has the potential to improve
51 survival outcomes in LMICs.[1] He also mentioned that oral metronomic chemotherapy is a cost-
52 effective alternative approach compared to pazopanib in advanced soft tissue sarcoma.[2] He also
53 mentioned about the Indian medicine system e.g. Use of ginger powder as a supportive therapy in
54 improving chemotherapy-induced nausea and vomiting (CINV). He shared the results of his study
55 on the antiemetic effect of ginger powder versus placebo in children and young adults receiving
56 high emetogenic chemotherapy.[3] Further, the first evidence on the use of olanzapine in children
57 to prevent CINV, .[4] He then emphasized the establishment of multicentric collaborations to
58 improve standards of care, giving an example of INPOG's (<https://www.inphog.org/>) status as of
59 2021 describing 31 studies of which seven had completed and 16 studies are currently ongoing
60 with an objective of generating evidence on outcomes of current clinical practice. At the end, he
61 highlighted solutions for efficient way of conducting research in LMICs by coming together and
62 being cohesive and innovative, that could eventually bring out easily affordable options for the
63 world.

64

65 The second lecture of the symposium was given by Dr. Smita Kayal on the topic **‘Choosing**
66 **appropriate research questions in precision and personalized oncology’**. She started to discuss
67 domains such as genomics, transcriptomic, metabolomics, and proteomics. Then she discussed the
68 following questions: What is precision oncology? Why do we need precision oncology? What are
69 the goals of precision oncology? What is the spectrum of cancer-etio-pathogenesis, diagnosis, and

70 management- which can be precisely personalized? What are the tools/approaches for precision &
71 personalized medicine (PPM)? How to identify the research problem and choose/design a research
72 question to answer the questions as mentioned above. Following, she spoke about the rights of
73 medication administration with 1) Right patient 2) Right drug 3) Right time 4) Right route 5) Right
74 dose 6) Right reason 7) Right documentation. She also highlighted that data on risk factors,
75 screening, diagnosis, staging, prognosis, treatment, response, and follow-up can help in the
76 evolution of precision oncology. She also highlighted the fact that the use of conventional
77 chemotherapies using targeted approaches could improve precision medicine outcomes. She stated
78 the PICO model P=Patient/Population/Problem I=Intervention/Exposure, C=Comparison
79 O=Outcomes as a well-built research question. To summarize, she concluded that further research
80 is required to see if genetic tools can help tailor therapies in high-risk patients.

81

82 In addition, the session continued with a panel discussion on topic ‘**The role of molecular**
83 **diagnostics in the delivery of precision therapy**’. The panelists included Dr. Archana Singh, Dr.
84 Sameer Bakhshi, Dr. Nithya Ramnath, Dr. BH Srinivas, Dr. Smita Kayal, and Dr. Jaikumar. The
85 discussion was moderated by Dr. Biswajit Dubashi, narrating specific questions seeking input from
86 the panelists like passenger versus driver mutation, incorporation of artificial intelligence in aiding
87 management along with molecular diagnostics. Individual versus population-based precision care-
88 Precision public health.

89 The discussion started with an interaction with case scenarios that highlighted key points on
90 diagnosis, treatment, monitoring, risk assessment, prognosis, pharmacogenomics, and its
91 importance in precision cancer. The case scenarios discussed shed light on the following: 1. The
92 principles of molecular tests i.e., how to select these tests in practice? 2. molecular diagnostic

93 testing? 3. about molecular testing in a newly diagnosed metastatic setting 4. Molecular testing in
94 a patient who had exhausted all approved drugs? 5. Use of molecular tests in the adjuvant setting
95 6. Role of genetic polymorphisms in guiding treatment 7. Failure of personalized therapy using
96 molecular tests. Interactive discussion on the passenger versus driver mutations and its role in
97 targeting tumors for precision therapy is continued. Further, the panel discussed about the type of
98 biochemical changes associated with tumors, such as somatic mutations, inherited variations,
99 polymorphisms, gene amplification or copy number variation, gene expression changes, protein
100 overexpression, protein loss, and mutation. Furthermore, Dr.BH Srinivas and Dr. Archna
101 explained the principles of molecular tests and how to select specific tests such as
102 immunohistochemistry (IHC), fluorescence in situ hybridisation (FISH), targeted Reverse
103 transcription polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR), targeted sequencing, whole genome/exome
104 sequencing, microbiome study, circulating tumour cells, functional assay transcriptomic studies,
105 proteomics, and metabolomics using case scenarios in a diagnostic molecular testing and
106 concluded with the translation potential of complex disease genomics in improvements to human
107 health are achieved through various enabling milestones at different translational.[5]

108 The next session was addressed by Dr. Archna Singh on the topic '**Approaches to understanding**
109 **mitochondrial dysfunction in leukemia**'. She covered the essential biological functions of
110 mitochondria and how mutations in mitochondrial genes or altered mitochondrial bioenergetics
111 supports cancer cell sustenance. Then she explained the role of mitochondria in malignant
112 transformation covering the genetic, environmental, and tissue origin differences between
113 tumours. She discussed about mitochondrial biogenesis and apoptosis in the PGC-1 α as a central
114 regulator of mitochondrial biogenesis through the interaction with multiple transcription
115 factors.[6] Furthermore, she commented on how mitophagy can affect tumour initiation and

116 metastasis. She then spoke about metabolic reprogramming, bioenergetic profiles, ultrastructural
117 changes, and reactive oxygen species generation.[7] She also presented data from her work that
118 demonstrated the role of mitochondrial dysfunction in acute lymphoblastic leukemia and myeloid
119 leukemia. She concluded that specific assays for the mitochondrial function would help to identify
120 the various oncogenic pathways and the increased expression of *TFAM*, *POLG*, *POLRMT*, *MYC*,
121 *ND3* genes, and the higher mtDNA copy number was significantly higher in AML and an
122 independent predictor of aggressive disease, was associated with lower event free survival, and
123 overall survival.[8]

124

125 She then summarized her talk by delineating factors that contributed to the dichotomous effects of
126 mitochondrial function on specific susceptibilities for cancer subtypes that will help us test novel
127 therapeutic targets or mitochondrial-targeted therapies.

128

129 In the next session, Dr. Girish Chinnaswamy spoke about the “**Landscape of precision medicine**
130 **in Paediatric oncology**”. He narrated the success story of childhood cancer survival outcomes
131 and highlighted the higher incidence (~24%) of toxicities that occur in Paediatric cancer
132 patients.[9] Furthermore, he also marked the requirements for improved outcomes in high-risk
133 neuroblastoma, undifferentiated/metastatic sarcomas, bone sarcomas, metastatic ewing/osteo
134 medulloblastomas/gliomas that continued to show a poor therapeutic outcome.[10] Speaker also
135 shared the evidence on the rare presence of hypermutant phenotypes in children compared to
136 adults. Furthermore, he discussed how the driver mutations are more exclusive to tumors and are
137 not shared between different types of cancer. He also listed problems faced in clinical studies in
138 children, such as late diagnosis of most tumors and possibility of greater benefit when diagnosed

139 early. He mentioned the collateral benefits of childhood cancer treatment, including the following:
140 refinement of diagnosis-better risk stratification in neurooncology and sarcomas; identification of
141 germline mutations via family screening/surveillance and immunotherapy. The speaker also
142 emphasized that identifying mismatch repair deficiency (benefit of surveillance) had a better
143 survival benefit in several (e.g., brain, gastrointestinal tumors. He then highlighted the benefit of
144 precision oncology in Paediatric tumors by giving examples of usage of BRAF inhibitors, ALK
145 rearrangement/mutations in neuroblastoma, and anaplastic large cell lymphoma. He then
146 mentioned about the systematic review that answered the question about the clinical utility of
147 precision medicine in Paediatric oncology.[11] Finally, he spoke about the limitations of precision
148 oncology in children, which were as follows: rare nature of Paediatric cancers, slow drug
149 development process; limited evidence on the use of novel targeted agents with safe and effective
150 dosing, in children; lack of direct comparisons with traditional chemotherapy; inconsistent
151 reporting of outcomes in Paediatric precision medicine studies; limited data on health economic
152 assessment in developing countries. He then concluded the talk, that it is feasible to implement
153 precision medicine by having multicenter international collaborations with multidisciplinary teams
154 addressing the issues delineated above.

155
156 The second keynote session was addressed by Dr. A.D.R Alwin Huitema on: “**Precision dosing**
157 **of anti-cancer drugs in children**”. He explained about the importance of clinical pharmacology
158 in Paediatric oncology, focusing on fludarabine in CART-Cell therapy. He then explained the
159 fludarabine exposure progression-free survival rates from fludarabine exposure in Paediatric
160 patients.[12] Exposure-response association studies emphasize the importance of optimal dosage
161 therapy to achieve optimal therapeutic benefits. He highlighted the hallmarks of pharmacokinetic

162 variability, which are also caused by drug-drug interactions, drug-food interactions, and
163 differences in drug metabolism in addition to oncogenic and physiological differences in growing
164 children. He then emphasized that precision medicine plays an important role in choosing the right
165 drug for the right patient and highlighted the importance of choosing the right dose, especially in
166 children.[13, 14] He then provided solutions to achieve this through pharmacogenetics and
167 pharmacogenomics; pharmacokinetic profiling and therapeutic drug monitoring;
168 pharmacodynamic profiling of drugs; and appropriate drug formulation. He further continued his
169 talk by providing two examples. The first example was pharmacogenotyping and predicted clinical
170 outcomes (response/side effects or survival), i.e.... association of variants in drug metabolizing
171 enzymes encoding genes *CYP2C9*, *CYP2C19*, *CYP2D6*, *CYP3A4*, *CYP3A5*, *TPMT*, *NUDT15*,
172 *UGT1A1* on how they influence therapeutic outcomes in paediatric oncology.[14] Furthermore, he
173 presented a case report on whether severe toxicity due to methotrexate and vincristine therapy can
174 be explained by pharmacogenetics. Then he explained a future scenario that has a workflow
175 starting from whole exome sequencing of data at diagnosis and then extracting pharmacogenetic
176 variants using the PharmCAT tool. Following, the speaker explained about the interpretation of
177 the dosing on the basis of variant alleles. He continued his talk with the second example on
178 pharmacokinetic (PK) studies in neonates and infants on how it is challenging to perform PK
179 studies in such population.[15] He explained the variability in PK among neonates and infants
180 contributed mainly by changes in expression of drug-metabolizing enzymes and altered
181 distribution of the drug.[16] Then, he spoke about the empirical dosing of vincristine and how
182 tubulin expression was highly age dependent and could influence the PK of vincristine in
183 children.[17] He finally summarized his talk emphasizing the utility of modelling and simulations

184 in Paediatric oncology; for dose selection of chemotherapeutic drugs; incorporating all influencing
185 factors.

186

187 The program was then followed by a debate on **“Tumor agnostic therapy is the way forward in**
188 **cancer management’** by Dr. Nishil Gowda and Dr. Archana Sasi. Dr. Nishil spoke in favor of the
189 topic. He began by defining tumor agnostic therapy as the use of drug treatment that targets a
190 specific molecular alteration across multiple cancer types irrespective of organ, tissue, and tumor
191 subtype. He mentioned multiple drugs that had been approved by the FDA for tumor agnostic
192 therapy such as Pembrolizumab and NTRK inhibitors. Subsequently, he spoke about the safety
193 and efficacy of NTRK inhibitors (Larotrectinib[18] and Entrectinib [19]), BRAF V600E
194 inhibitors[20] (Dabrafenib and, Trametinib), and RET fusion inhibitor[21] (Selpercatinib). In
195 addition, he mentioned that the approval of these drugs was based on master protocols also referred
196 to as umbrella trials. The major limitation of these trials was the limited number of patients in each
197 molecular subtype. After that, Dr. Archana spoke against the topic. She started by describing the
198 concept of tumor-agnostic therapy. Then, she spoke about the lineage dependency model for
199 human cancers by providing a few examples. In addition, she spoke about the impact of tissue-
200 specific signaling pathways and gave the example of BRAF inhibitors which have been seen to
201 produce better responses in melanoma as compared to colorectal cancers. Further, she described
202 the PIK3CA pathway inhibitors, wherein therapy responses are influenced by mediators upstream
203 and downstream, thus rendering the class of drugs ineffective for use in a tissue-agnostic manner.
204 She explained how intratumor heterogeneity, epigenetic architecture, tumor microenvironment,
205 and the type of mutations influence therapeutic responses Finally, she highlighted the challenges

206 involved in translating the use of tissue agnostic therapy into clinical practice and emphasized that
207 the histologic context must always be kept in mind.

208

209 The next session was continued by Prof. Jayanthi on “**Therapeutic Drug Monitoring (TDM) in**
210 **the era of precision medicine**”. She started the session by describing about the TDM and criteria
211 for TDM (e.g., narrow therapeutic index). In addition, she introduced progress in cancer survival
212 rates and emphasised the toxicity potential of anticancer drugs. Following, speaker narrated when
213 to use area under the curve drug concentrations (AUC; using multiple blood samples) and when to
214 use trough levels (single blood sample) to understand the exposure response relationship of chemo
215 and immunosuppressive therapies. Then she enlisted available evidence on utility of TDM in
216 anticancer drug therapy.[22] Further, she explained the process of executing TDM, beginning with
217 sample collection, sample storage, sample analysis (HPLC/LCMS), and data analysis.[23] She
218 gave few examples of the usage of TDM in anti-cancer drugs, such as the use of fluorouracil dose
219 adjustment based on PK follow-up in colorectal cancer patients.[24, 25] Finally, she concluded
220 the talk mentioning the challenges with respect to the use/implementation of TDM and the need
221 for TDM more widely in the oncology settings. She suggested that developing validated multidrug
222 assays to quantify several anticancer drugs simultaneously could be advantageous in limited
223 resource settings.

224

225 The next session was delivered by the program director Dr. CRS Uppugunduri on "**Role of**
226 **Pharmacogenomics in reducing toxicity in acute lymphoblastic leukemia treatment-A Pilot**
227 **Study Report of a study MPGx-INDALL.**" He compared the incidences and survival rates of
228 leukemia in India and Europe.[26] He then addressed the issue of treatment-related toxicities in

229 LMICs such as India and the factors associated with treatment-related toxicities[27]. He then spoke
230 about a pilot observational retrospective study on how genetic variants in *NUDT15* could predict
231 the occurrence of early hematological toxicities in ALL children and adults undergoing
232 maintenance therapy with 6-mercaptopurine and methotrexate.[28] He then gave an overview of
233 the methodology of candidate gene selection. He then spoke about an Indo-Swiss collaborative
234 research project titled "Molecular and pharmacogenetic marker evaluation with the toxicity and
235 clinical response of ALL treatment in children (MPGx-INDALL)" for children undergoing
236 chemotherapy protocol and undergoing treatment-related toxicity. He then delineated the primary
237 and secondary objectives of MPGx-INDALL by hypothesizing that there are ethnic variations exist
238 in both germline and somatic mutations that may serve as a prognostic marker of treatment. The
239 speaker discussed the study methodology. Finally, he concluded that children at high risk of
240 developing toxicities with chemotherapy could be identified by screening pharmacogenetic
241 variants that are to be defined in order to reduce the number needed to genotype for each ethnicity
242 with an objective of implement or develop policies on preemptive pharmacogenetic testing.

243

244 The last session of the symposium was on "**How precision medicine has changed outcomes in**
245 **lung cancer**" by Dr. Nithya Ramnath. She narrated historical context of stage IV non-small cell
246 lung cancer. She explained that there was a declining incidence coupled with the introduction of
247 new treatments being introduced.[29] She then gave an overview of the spectrum of oncogenic
248 driver mutations in lung adenocarcinoma and their incidence rates. She then described the
249 outcomes of four targets: 1. EGFR mutant lung adenocarcinoma 2. ALK-rearranged lung
250 adenocarcinoma 3. ROS1 rearranged lung adenocarcinoma 4. PDL1>50% lung adenocarcinoma.
251 Furthermore, she spoke about the Trailblazer for precision oncology in Lung Cancer to target

252 mutations in the EGFR gene. She spoke about the evaluation of alectinib versus ceritinib in ALK
253 positive nonsmall cell lung cancer in Phase 2 trials and real-world data.[30] Following, the speaker
254 discussed about immune checkpoint inhibitors targeting PDL-1 in non-small cell lung cancer. She
255 gave an overview of the study, which demonstrated the use of pembrolizumab with better
256 progression-free survival and overall survival compared to chemotherapy in metastatic nonsmall
257 cell lung cancer with PD-L1 tumor proportion score>50%.[31] Finally, she concluded that
258 precision oncology is encompassing many factors and has enabled the prolongation of lung cancer
259 survival. Factors included precision screening, precision staging, precision therapies, precision
260 radiation, and next-generation data-driven precision oncology.

261 **Attendance and Feedback Responses from the participants:**

262 At the end of the symposium, 85.2% of the participants gave feedback on the event as indicated in
263 Table 1, 2

264

265 **Future perspectives:**

266 **Based on feedback from Participants:**

267 The objective of this symposium is to familiarize precision oncology concepts to the target
268 audience and to spread awareness among residents in training on its utility in cancer care based on
269 available evidence from literatures and clinical investigations used currently clinical care and to
270 establish the novel therapeutic strategies to prevent the treatment related toxicities. A hundred
271 percent of our participants choose to conduct such a symposium on regular basis in the future,
272 possibly with topics such as how to implement laboratory-based findings (from bench side to the
273 bedside) in clinical care set up.

274

275 **Conflicts of interest:** None to declare

276 **Data Sharing:** None

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293 **Event held at Organization:** Jawaharlal Institute of Postgraduate Medical Education and
294 Research, Puducherry, India

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296 **Event Date:** 21.11.2022

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302 **Abbreviation:**

3031. ALK - Anaplastic lymphoma kinase

3042. ALL - Acute Lymphoblastic Leukemia

3053. AML - Acute Myeloid Leukemia

3064. BRAF - serine/threonine-protein kinase B-Raf.

3075. CART – Chimeric antigen receptor in T cell

3086. CINV - Chemotherapy induced nausea and vomiting

3097. *CYP2C9* - Cytochrome P450 family 2 subfamily C member 9

3108. *CYP2C19* - *Cytochrome* P450 family 2 subfamily C member 19

3119. *CYP2D6* - *Cytochrome* P450 family 2 subfamily D member 6

31210. *CYP3A4* - Cytochrome P450 family 3 subfamily A member 4

31311. *CYP3A5* - Cytochrome P450 family 23subfamily A member 5

31412. EGFR - Epidermal growth factor receptors

31513. FDA – Food Drug Administration

31614. FISH - Fluorescence in situ hybridisation

31715. IHC - Immunohistochemistry

31816. INPOG's – Indian Paediatric Hematology Oncology Group

31917. JIPMER – Jawaharlal Institute of Postgraduate Medical Education and Research

32018. LMICs - Low-middle-income countries

32119. mtDNA - Mitochondrial DNA

32220. MPGx-INDALL - Molecular and Pharmacogenetic marker evaluation in relation to the toxicity

323 and clinical response of Acute Lymphoblastic Leukemia (ALL) treatment in Indian children

- 32421. *MYC* - myc proto-oncogene protein
- 32522. *ND3* - NADH dehydrogenase 3
- 32623. NADH - Nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (NAD) + hydrogen (H)
- 32724. NTRK - neurotrophic tyrosine receptor kinase gene fusion.
- 32825. *NUDT15* - Nudix hydrolase 15
- 32926. PDL1 - Programmed death ligand 1
- 33027. PGC-1 α - Peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor-gamma coactivator
- 33128. PI3K/ AKT - Phosphoinositide 3-kinase
- 33229. PIK3CA - Phosphatidylinositol-4,5-bisphosphate 3-kinase catalytic subunit alpha
- 33330. PK - Pharmacokinetic
- 33431. PPM - Precision & Personalized Medicine
- 33532. *POLG* - Polymerase gamma
- 33633. *POLRMT* - mitochondrial RNA polymerase
- 33734. RAF/MEK - Rapidly Accelerated Fibrosarcoma.
- 33835. ROS1 - ROS proto-oncogene 1
- 33936. RT-PCR - reverse transcription polymerase chain reaction
- 34037. TDM - Therapeutic Drug Monitoring
- 34138. *TFAM* - Mitochondrial transcription factor A
- 34239. *TPMT* - Thiopurine S-methyl transferase
- 34340. *UGT1A1* – Uridyl diphosphate glucuronosyl transferase 1A1

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453 **Table 1: The symposium feedback by participants (in person and virtual) in terms of the quality of Lectures, Content, and**
 454 **Usefulness.**

S.No	Topic	Excellent (%)	Very good (%)	Good (%)	Average (%)	Below average (%)
1.	Challenges and opportunities in translational oncology from Indian perspective: Focus on oncology”	57.1	42.9	-	-	-
2.	Choosing appropriate research questions in precision and personalized oncology	61.9	35.7	2.4	-	-
3.	Role of molecular diagnostics in delivering precision therapy	52.4	45.2	2.4	-	-
4.	Approaches to understanding mitochondrial dysfunction in leukemia	50.0	42.9	7.1	-	-
5.	The landscape of precision medicine in Paediatric oncology	59.5	35.7	4.8	-	-
6.	Precision dosing of anticancer drugs in children	57.1	38.1	4.8	-	-
7.	Tumor agnostic therapy is the way forward in cancer management	57.1	38.1	4.8	-	-

8.	TDM (Therapeutic Drug Monitoring) In the era of precision medicine	64.3	33.3	2.4	-	-
9.	Role of pharmacogenomics in reducing toxicity in acute lymphoblastic leukemia Treatment	61.9	33.3	4.8	-	-
10.	How precision medicine has changed outcomes in lung cancer	69.0	31.0	-	-	-

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456 **Table 2: The symposium feedback by the participants (in person and virtual):**

S.No	Topic	Excellent (%)	Very good (%)	Good (%)	Average (%)	Below average (%)
1.	Overall relevance to the content	59.03	37.62	3.35	-	-
2.	Improvement of knowledge and understanding	33.3	50.0	16.7	-	-
3.	Response of Resource Persons to participants questions	92.9	7.1	-	-	-
4.	Improvement of your domain expertise	28.6	50.0	21.4	-	-
5.	Value of precision oncology in future	66.7	28.6	4.7	-	-

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